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Research paper

Machine learning techniques for estimating high-temperature mechanical behavior of high strength steels

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for predicting the mechanical behavior of materials by analyzing stress-strain data from tensile tests. In this study, we present a novel ML-based framework for accurately predicting the high-temperature mechanical properties of high-strength steels (HSS) using reduction factor datasets. A key contribution of this work is the development of an extensive experimental dataset through tensile testing of HSS specimens with varying thicknesses and temperatures, further expanded with over 450 additional data points covering a diverse range of material conditions. Various ML models—including Lasso Regression, Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, Extreme Gradient Boosting, Support Vector Regression, and Adaptive Boosting were rigorously evaluated to determine their predictive capabilities. The GB model achieved the highest accuracy, with an adjusted coefficient of determination (R^2) exceeding 0.98, outperforming conventional regression approaches. The proposed framework was validated against experimental data, demonstrating strong agreement and confirming its effectiveness in capturing complex nonlinear material behavior. This study provides a significant advancement over traditional empirical methods by offering a data-driven approach for predicting HSS performance under elevated temperatures, facilitating the design of safer and more efficient structural components in high-temperature applications.

1. Introduction

Machine learning (ML) has emerged as a powerful tool for addressing complex challenges in engineering and materials science [1,2]. Recently, ML applications have shown great promise in predicting the mechanical properties of various materials under both ambient and elevated temperature conditions [3,4]. These advances offer significant improvements in both efficiency and safety for structural engineering applications, particularly in high-stakes environments. High-strength steels (HSS), known for their excellent strength-to-weight ratios, contribute to lighter yet more durable structures. However, ensuring the safe design of these materials under extreme conditions, such as during fire exposure, critically depends on accurately forecasting their mechanical behavior at elevated temperatures [5–7]. Accurately predicting the mechanical properties of steels at elevated temperatures is essential for the safe and cost-effective design of structures. Traditional prediction methods typically rely on the use of ‘reduction factors’ to estimate material performance under high-temperature conditions. However, these approaches often overlook important variables such as testing proto-

cols, manufacturing processes, and chemical composition. Moreover, they largely depend on fitting experimental data, which can lead to reduced prediction accuracy, particularly for HSS [8].

Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of ML in predicting the mechanical properties of steels at elevated temperatures. For instance, Shaheen et al. developed an ML model that utilized chemical composition data as input features to predict the mechanical properties of high-strength steels (HSS) at high temperatures [8]. The model was trained and validated using data from experimental test programs, yielding excellent performance, with very low prediction error and a high correlation coefficient for strength and hardness reduction factors. In another study, Yang et al. applied ML to predict the swelling rate of irradiated type 316 stainless steels [9]. By constructing a dataset that incorporated environmental and material parameters, they employed multiple regression models to capture the complex relationships influencing swelling behavior. The results demonstrated that ML could effectively predict these behaviors with reasonable accuracy, closely aligning with experimental data.

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Recent advancements in machine learning (ML) have significantly improved the predictive modeling of material properties under complex conditions. For example, Shafighfar et al. [10] used a stacked ML framework to predict the compressive strength of steel fiber reinforced concrete (SFRC) exposed to elevated temperatures, achieving $R^2 = 0.92$ with 307 experimental datasets. Their study highlighted ML's ability to model complex nonlinear relationships between factors like heating rate and material composition. Building on this, our study applies ML to predict the ultimate stress of high-strength steels (HSS) at elevated temperatures, using experimental and literature based data for robust predictions. Furthermore, Dorbane et al. explored machine learning (ML) methods Gaussian process regression, neural networks, and boosted trees for predicting stress strain curves of Al6061-T6 aluminum alloy across 25–300 °C, achieving high accuracy with an R^2 of 0.998 and a mean absolute error of 0.213% using the neural network model. Notably, particle fracture dominated at ≤ 200 °C, while interfacial decohesion prevailed at 300 °C [11,12]. In addition, the authors develop effective data -driven approaches to forecast the stress-strain curves of Al6061-T6 aluminum alloy base material and welded using Friction Stir Welding (FSW) technique under different temperature conditions, with a focus on using LSTM and GRU deep learning models to capture temporal dependencies and predict material behavior, demonstrating GRU's superior efficiency and performance [13].

Comparative studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of various ML algorithms in predicting the mechanical properties of steels. Chen et al. applied ensemble methods, such as Gradient Boosting and Random Forest, to predict stress-strain curves from the microstructural characteristics of additively manufactured mild steel, achieving superior predictive performance and robustness compared to traditional regression techniques [14]. Jin et al. investigated the prediction of notch fatigue life in micro-shot peened 25CrMo4 alloy steel, demonstrating that ML methods outperformed conventional fracture mechanics approaches. By incorporating features like dislocation density and irradiation fluence, their models provided more accurate predictions and valuable insights into the material's behavior under stress [15]. Pan et al. combined small punch test data with machine learning techniques to predict the mechanical properties of pressure vessel steels, showing that integrating experimental data with ML models can result in highly accurate predictions [16]. Millner et al. applied ML to predict the mechanical properties of steel sheets produced through an industrial process. Their study underscored the ability of ML models to effectively capture variations in mechanical properties arising from different production routes [17].

The research presented in this manuscript incorporates experimental tensile test data on S235 steel, with varying thicknesses and temperatures, to generate an initial dataset. This was further expanded with over 450 reduction factor curves from published studies, representing diverse material classes. Advanced ML models, including Gradient Boosting (GB), Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), and Adaptive Boosting (ADA), were employed to analyze this comprehensive dataset. Among these, GB demonstrated exceptional performance, achieving an adjusted (R^2) value greater than 0.98, and was particularly adept at capturing nonlinear behaviors at extreme temperatures. This work highlights the potential of ML-driven approaches to replace reduction factor-based methods, offering more robust, efficient, and reliable predictions of material behavior. The insights gained through this methodology pave the way for designing safer and more efficient structures under elevated temperatures, providing a significant step forward in the field of high-temperature materials analysis.

2. Methods

2.1. Experimental methods

The research objective of our experiments is defined and centers on evaluating the load-bearing capacities of high-strength steel (HSS)

Fig. 1. Dimensions and shape of the tensile test specimens (a), and the tensile test setup for HSS measurements (b).

specimens under elevated temperatures. Specifically, the experiments aim to develop a robust data-driven framework for predicting the ultimate stress of HSS, which is crucial for ensuring the safety and reliability of structural components exposed to fire or high-temperature environments. To achieve this, tensile tests were conducted on specimens of varying thicknesses and temperatures, generating foundational datasets to assess the impact of these factors on the reduction of material strength. Furthermore, the experimental data serve as a basis for validating machine learning models and comparing their predictive capabilities, ensuring a comprehensive understanding of HSS behavior under such conditions. The specimens were S235 cold-formed steels (CFS) with thicknesses of 4, 6, 8, 10, and 12 mm and were considered as bare steel samples without any coatings or protective layers. Prior to testing, the surfaces of the specimens were carefully cleaned, ensuring no additional treatments were applied. The dimensions and shape of the tensile test specimens are shown in Fig. 1a). The Thermcore PLF 130/25 brand furnace was equipped with a K-type thermocouple for precise temperature control and monitoring. The specimens were heated incrementally, starting from room temperature (23 °C) and increasing by 100 °C intervals up to 1100 °C. During the heating process, the temperature was increased at a controlled rate, and once the target temperature was reached, the specimens were maintained at that temperature for a specified period to ensure uniform thermal exposure. After reaching the target temperature, the specimens were immediately subjected to axial tensile testing without any cooling phase.

The tensile tests were conducted using an Instron testing machine at a controlled strain rate of 2.5 mm/min, in accordance with ASTM E8/E8M-21 (1) standards [18], where dog-bone-shaped specimens were utilized to achieve uniform stress distribution across the gauge length and to minimize stress concentrations at the gripping regions. The samples were subjected to axial tensile testing after being heated to the target temperature and held for a stabilization period of 20 minutes. Subsequently, a steady-state tensile test was performed under isothermal conditions, maintaining a constant specimen temperature while applying a controlled displacement rate of 0.3 mm/min. These tests were essential to assess the effects of high-temperature exposure on the mechanical properties of the specimens. Axial Tensile Tests: During the axial tensile tests, the specimens were subjected to an axial tensile

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of the methodology used to select the optimal stacked ML model and evaluate its performance.

force to measure their response under mechanical stress. This approach simulates real-life loading conditions, allowing for the observation of changes in structural behavior, as illustrate in Fig. 1b). Key parameters measured during these tests included tensile strength, yield strength, and strain at failure. These measurements provided comprehensive insights into the specimens' performance, particularly their load-bearing capacity at elevated temperatures [5]. The results from the axial tensile tests highlighted how incremental temperature increases influenced the structural performance of the specimens. The application of axial force allowed for the evaluation of the extent to which the materials retained their load-bearing capacities after exposure to specified temperature levels.

2.2. Supervised machine learning methods

To find the optimal model for prediction the compressive strength of steel materials, seven distinct ML models were utilized. The algorithms utilized in this study include (1) Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO) [19], (2) Gradient Boosting (GB) [20], (3) Random Forest (RF) [21], (4) Support Vector Regression (SVR) [22], (5) Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) [23], and (7) Adapting Boosting (ADA) [24] that implemented in the scikit-learn machine learning library [25]. The schematic representation of our methodology for selecting the optimal stacked ML model and evaluating its performance is shown in Fig. 2. Selecting appropriate hyper-parameters used for each algorithm, excluding information on their default values. The hyperparameters in Table 1 were fine-tuned using grid search and 10-fold cross validation to achieve the highest accuracy.

The Stacking Regressor models used in this study combine multiple regression models to improve predictive performance. This method leverages different models' strenghts, stacking them to create a robust final prediction [19–24]. The basic idea is to train several base models (level- 0 models) and then use their predictions as input features to train a meta model (level- 1 model), which makes the final predictions [26–29]. This model can be mathematically described as follows:

1. Base Models (Level-0 Models) Let's denote:
 - \mathbf{X} as the input feature matrix with n samples and p features.
 - \mathbf{y} as the target vector with n samples.
 - M as the number of base models.

Each base model m_i (where $i \in \{1, 2, \dots, M\}$) learns a function f_i that maps the input features \mathbf{X} to the predictions $\hat{y}_i = f_i(\mathbf{X})$

2. Creating Meta-Features: The predictions from the base models are used to create a new feature matrix \mathbf{Z} , often referred to as the meta-features or level-1 features. Each column of \mathbf{Z} corresponds to the predictions from one base model: $\mathbf{Z} = [\hat{y}_1, \hat{y}_2, \dots, \hat{y}_M]$
So, \mathbf{Z} is an $n \times M$ matrix where each entry Z_{ij} is the prediction of the j -th base model for the i -th sample.
3. Meta-Model (Level-1 Model) A meta-model g is trained on the meta-features \mathbf{Z} to learn the final mapping to the target $\hat{y} = g(\mathbf{Z})$

The meta-model can be any regression model (e.g., linear regression, ridge regression, etc.). For example, if the meta-model is a linear regression model, then $\hat{y} = \mathbf{Z}\mathbf{w} + b$ where:

- \mathbf{w} is the vector of weights.
 - b is the bias term.
4. Cross-Validation for Base Models To avoid overfitting and ensure that the base models do not see the entire training data during their training phase, we typically use cross-validation. In k -fold cross-validation:
 - The training data is split into k folds.
 - Each base model is trained on $k - 1$ folds and makes predictions on the remaining fold.
 - This process is repeated k times to generate out-of-fold predictions for the entire training data.

The out-of-fold predictions are used to create the meta-features for training the meta-model.

2.2.1. Least absolute shrinkage and selection operator (LASSO) regression

It is a linear regression method that includes a regularization term to enforce sparsity in the model preventing overfitting [19]. The objective function for lasso regression is:

$$\min_{\beta} \left\{ \frac{1}{2n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \mathbf{x}_i^T \beta)^2 + \lambda \sum_{j=1}^p |\beta_j| \right\} \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{y} is the $n \times 1$ vector of target values. \mathbf{X} is the $n \times p$ matrix of input features. β is the $p \times 1$ vector of regression coefficients. $\lambda \geq 0$ is the regularization parameter. The properties of this model are: **Shrinkage**: The regularization term encourages smaller coefficients. **Sparsity**: Lasso can set some coefficients exactly to zero, performing variable selection. The lasso objective function is convex but not differentiable due to the $L1$ norm. It can be efficiently solved using techniques like coordinate descent or least angle regression.

2.2.2. Gradient boosting (GB)

Gradient Boosting is an ensemble method that builds multiple decision trees sequentially. Each tree corrects the errors of its predecessor, leading to improved accuracy [20]. Gradient Boosting is known for its ability to handle complex, non-linear relationships between features.

2.2.3. Random forest (RF)

Random Forest is an ensemble method that constructs multiple decision trees during training and outputs the average prediction of the individual trees [21]. It is robust to overfitting and performs well with high-dimensional data.

2.2.4. Support vector regression (SVR)

Support Vector Regression (SVR) is a robust machine learning method derived from Support Vector Machines (SVM), designed to predict continuous values. Unlike classical regression models, SVR maps input data into a high-dimensional feature space using kernels, enabling the capture of nonlinear relationships [22,20]. It seeks to fit a regression hyperplane that approximates data points within a defined margin of tolerance, controlled by the epsilon parameter. The model's complexity is balanced by the regularization parameter C , which manages the trade-off between accuracy and generalization, making SVR effective for modeling complex material properties.

2.2.5. Extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost)

Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) is an optimized version of Gradient Boosting that offers enhanced performance and efficiency [23]. It includes regularization techniques to avoid overfitting and handles sparse data effectively.

Table 1
Hyperparameters of machine learning models.

ML	Variations	value	Optimal
LASSO	Regularization strength (alpha)	0.01, 0.1, 1.0	0.1
GB	Number of boosting stages (n_estimators)	100, 200, 300	200
	Learning rate	0.01, 0.1, 0.3	0.1
	Maximum depth of the individual estimators	3, 5, 7	5
	Minimum samples required to split a node	2, 5, 10	2
	Minimum samples required at each leaf node	1, 2, 5	1
RF	Subsample	0.8, 0.9,	1
	Number of trees in the forest	50, 100, 200	100
	Maximum depth of each tree	10, 20, 30	20
	Minimum samples required to split a node	2, 5, 10	2
	Minimum samples required at each leaf node	1, 2, 5	2
	Criterion for splitting	'gini', 'entropy'	entropy
	Maximum number of features	'auto', sqrt(n_features), 0.5	sqrt(n_features)
XGBoost	Maximum depth of trees	3, 5, 7	5
	Learning rate	0.01, 0.1, 0.3	0.1
	Number of trees (n_estimators)	100, 200, 300	200
	Minimum sum of instance weight	1, 5, 10	1
	Gamma	0, 0.1, 0.3	0.1
SVR	Regularization parameters (lambda, alpha)	0.01, 0.1, 1.0	0.1
	Choice of kernel	'linear', 'poly', 'rbf'	rbf
	Kernel coefficient	0.1, 1.0, 10.0	0.1
	Regularization parameter	0.1, 1.0, 10.0	1.0
ADA	Base Estimator	'DecisionTreeClassifier', 'SVC'	'DecisionTreeClassifier'
	Number of estimators (n_estimators)	50, 100, 200	100
	Learning rate	0.01, 0.1, 1.0	0.1
	Algorithm	'SAMME', 'SAMME.R'	'SAMME.R'

2.2.6. AdaBoost (ADA)

AdaBoost, short for Adaptive Boosting, is an ensemble method that combines weak learners to create a strong predictive model [24]. It adjusts the weights of incorrectly predicted instances, focusing more on difficult cases.

2.3. Model evaluation

The performance of the machine learning models was evaluated using several metrics, including [26–29]:

- **MAE (Mean Absolute Error):** Measures the average absolute difference between predicted and actual values and calculated as:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N |\text{TEST}_i - \text{PREDICTED}_i|. \quad (2)$$

- **Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):** A measure of the differences between predicted and actual values, and obtained as:

$$\text{RMSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N (\text{TEST}_i - \text{PREDICTED}_i)^2. \quad (3)$$

- **Coefficient of Determination:** A statistical measure that indicates how well the regression predictions approximate the real data points usually calculated as:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N (\text{TEST}_i - \text{PREDICTED}_i)^2}{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^N (\text{TEST}_i - \text{TEST}_{\text{ave}})^2}. \quad (4)$$

To mitigate the risk of overfitting in the machine learning models, a combination of rigorous strategies was implemented. Cross-validation techniques were employed to ensure the models' robustness and prevent reliance on specific training data, allowing performance evaluation across multiple data subsets and reducing the likelihood of overfitting to a single dataset. Hyperparameter tuning was conducted using systematic approaches such as grid search and random search to identify the optimal model complexity while avoiding overfitting. In ensemble learning models, such as Gradient Boosting and Random Forest, key parameters—including the maximum tree depth and the number of

estimators—were carefully controlled to prevent excessive model complexity and enhance generalization. These combined efforts ensure that the developed models achieve high accuracy while maintaining robustness and generalizability across diverse datasets. [20]. Each model's predictions were compared against the true values to assess their accuracy and reliability. The ensemble methods, such as Gradient Boosting and Random Forest, showed strong performance due to their ability to combine multiple models and reduce variance. The methodology outlined in this section demonstrates a comprehensive approach to predicting the mechanical properties of high-strength steels using advanced machine learning techniques.

The input variables that are used in our ML based model for understanding and modeling the mechanical behavior of high-strength steels under elevated temperature conditions are the following:

1. Temperature (°C) serves as the primary factor, representing the elevated temperatures applied during experiments and driving the reduction in mechanical properties
2. Material Thickness (mm), reflecting the geometric dimensions of the samples, significantly influences heat transfer and the mechanical response of the material
3. Ultimate Stress (MPa), defined as the maximum stress the material can withstand before failure
4. The Reduction Factor (χ), a normalized parameter derived from tensile test results, quantifies the degradation of mechanical properties as a function of temperature

These parameters are used as the target variable in the machine learning (ML) models. By employing multiple models and rigorous evaluation metrics, this study aims to provide reliable predictions that can enhance the safety and efficiency of structural designs under high-temperature conditions.

3. Results

The preprocessing stage involved cleaning the experimental data to remove any inconsistencies or missing values. This was achieved through the following steps: Data Cleaning) Removing duplicates and handling missing values through imputation method; Normalization)

Fig. 3. Experimentally data for stress-strain curves that is used by the models to predict ultimate stresses at different temperatures [5].

Scaling the data to a 0-1 range to ensure that all variables contribute equally to the model; and Feature Selection) Identifying the most relevant features for predicting mechanical properties based on domain knowledge and statistical methods. Several machine learning models were developed to predict the mechanical properties of high-strength steels.

We begin by experimentally obtaining stress–strain curves for each thickness value across a range of temperatures, as shown in Fig. 3 for a thickness of 8 mm, the reduction factor values were evaluated using the experimental data [5]. To enhance the visualization and understanding of the material’s nanomechanical response, we present the results obtained at low temperature in (a) and at high temperature in (b). These results are also valuable for acquiring raw data for other material’s thickness essential for the initial training dataset. To automate the characterization of these results and compute the ultimate stress at varying temperatures and thickness values, we developed a Python script. This script calculates the ultimate stress of each curve by analyzing its behavior and determining correlations with well-established stress–strain profiles from the literature [30]. Comparing two graphs by their correlation is an effective method for assessing the relationship between their trends and shapes. By utilizing the Pearson correlation coefficient, we quantify the linear relationship between the graphs, which indicates whether they move in the same or opposite directions or if they lack a linear association. For comparing multiple graphs, we used correlation matrices to visualize correlations across pairs of stress–strain curves at different temperatures, typically as heatmaps, to highlight similarity patterns.

In our study, we accounted for outliers, which can distort correlation values, emphasizing the importance of preprocessing or using robust correlation measures. Thus, in Fig. 4, we present a heatmap of the ultimate stress data for all samples considered in this study, computed by our in-house software, defining 44 values for the initial training data set. The results show a similar trend across different thickness values, with a noticeable drop in stress occurring at 500 °C for this material.

The reduction factor, χ is typically used to quantify the decrease in a material’s ultimate strength under specific conditions compared to a

Fig. 4. Heatmap of ultimate stress as a function of the temperature for different thickness.

Fig. 5. Comparison of experimental training data and test data for the reduction factor vs. temperature (8 mm thickness), with predictions from different ML-models.

reference state, in our case the samples at room temperature. This value is calculated as

$$\chi = \frac{\text{Ultimate Stress}[T]}{\text{Ultimate Stress}[rT]} \tag{5}$$

In Fig. 5 we present results for the reduction factor for all the samples as a function of the temperature. We also include the test data which is taken from the ultimate stress at a thickness of 8 mm, then applying different ML models, we select GB for being the one with better matching to the test data with a $R^2 = 0.98$. We have included a comparison with Adaptive Boosting (ADA) and Random Forest (RF) models to highlight the advantages of Gradient Boosting (GB) in capturing the trend and shape of the reduction factor curve. While all models achieved an R^2 value of 0.98, the GB model demonstrated a closer fit to the test data, making it the most accurate in reproducing the observed behavior. From our results, the reduction factor is greater than 1, when the heat is

Fig. 6. Correlation of reduction factor data taken from the literature which is used to build the training data set.

Table 2

Summary of Materials' Data for building the training data set with the steady method for the tensile test.

#	Ref.	Material Type	Temp. (°C)
1	[5]	S235	20–1100
2	[31]	G300-G500-G550	20–800
3	[32]	RQT701	20–800
4	[33]	S235	20–800
5	[34]	G450-G550	20–800
6	[35]	YSt-355-FR	20–800
7	[36]	SHP	20–900
8	[37]	Q345	20–800
9	[38]	Q960	20–800
10	[39]	G550	20–900
11	[40]	S350-S420-G500	20–700
12	[41]	S280 Gd+Z	20–800
13	[42]	S355	20–1000
14	[43]	HSA800	20–900
15	[44]	ZAR-345	20–600
16	[45]	G250-G450	20–700
17	[46]	G550	20–600
18	[47]	G250-G450	20–700
19	[48]	G550-G250	20–800
20	[49]	G550-G450	20–970

applied to the sample indicating strengthening mechanisms, which may form solid solutions or precipitates that enhance the material's strength. Processes like cold working or strain hardening, where the material is deformed to introduce dislocations and increase resistance to further deformation, can also result in an increase in strength. Although the model manages to reproduce the test data satisfactory, the data point at 500C is not well captured due to the lack of enough training data points.

3.1. Model for different classes of materials

The steady methodology was applied to the experimental data reported by [5], which is analyzed in this study. To ensure the model's general applicability across different material classes, we have incorporated reduction factor curves from the literature into our training data, as summarized in Table 2, which defined our training data set with 455 data points. Here, a steady method ensures reliable and reproducible results by maintaining a constant strain rate, stable loading, and consistent

temperature conditions. This approach minimizes errors and dynamic effects, accurately capturing stress-strain behavior for determining mechanical properties such as yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and elongation. The linear relationships between variables can be analyzed using the Pearson correlation coefficient, as shown in Fig. 6, which is calculated as follows [10,27]:

$$r = \frac{\sum(x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{(\sum(x_i - \bar{x})^2)(\sum(y_i - \bar{y})^2)}} \quad (6)$$

where the Pearson coefficient: \bar{x} is the average value of the x_i values, with same notation for y_i value, exhibiting similar trends across various material classes. The materials considered include commonly used steels such as S235, a low-carbon structural steel; G300, G500, and G550, which are high-strength, cold-formed steels; RQT701, a quenched and tempered steel; G450, a medium-strength cold-formed steel; Yst-355-FR, a low-alloyed steel with good fire resistance; SHP, a superior high-performance steel; Q345 and Q960, high-strength steels; S350 and S420, structural steels with high yield strength; S280, a galvanized steel for construction; S355, a high-strength, low-alloy steel; HSA800, a high-strength steel; ZAR-345, a cold-formed steel; and G250, a general-purpose structural steel.

To ensure the reliability and robustness of the developed machine learning models, a comprehensive validation strategy was employed, combining k -fold cross-validation with direct comparison against experimental data. In the k -fold cross-validation approach, the dataset was partitioned into k equal subsets, with the model iteratively trained on $k - 1$ subsets and evaluated on the remaining subset. This process was repeated across all folds to minimize potential bias and provide an unbiased estimate of the model's generalization performance. Furthermore, the predictive accuracy of the models was evaluated by benchmarking their outputs against experimentally measured stress-strain data obtained from tensile tests conducted on high-strength steel specimens across a range of temperatures and thicknesses. The comparison for different models is made between the test database for the HSA800 material with a thickness of 6 mm and various models' prediction as shown in Fig. 7. The linear relationship, illustrates this comparison where several models manage to represent the test results satisfactory. However, the GB-model is still dominant at high temperatures where a prediction would be necessary for industrial applications. In addition, we provide statistical metrics such as coefficient of determination (R^2), Root mean

Fig. 7. ML models scatter plot of training and testing.

Table 3

Performance comparison of different ML models.

Model	R ²	RMSE	MAE	RMSE/MAE
XGBoost	0.98	0.06	0.04	1.50
GB	0.98	0.05	0.04	1.25
LASSO	0.89	0.13	0.11	1.18
RF	0.98	0.06	0.04	1.50
ADA	0.98	0.05	0.04	1.25
SVR	0.97	0.06	0.06	1.00

squared error (RMSE), and Mean absolute error (MAE) for each model in Table 3. These parameters can be used as a guideline for selecting the best model for our task, where RMSE can be useful when large errors are undesirable and MAE provides a linear measure of the error without emphasizing large deviations.

Fig. 8 presents the prediction results for the reduction factor as a function of temperature for HSA800 steel with a thickness of 6 mm, using the Gradient Boosting (GB) and Adaptive Boosting (ADA) models. Both models demonstrate strong predictive performance, with coefficients of determination exceeding 0.98. However, while the ADA model accurately captures the reduction factor behavior at lower temperatures, it fails to follow the observed trend at higher temperatures. In contrast, the GB model successfully reproduces the behavior across the entire temperature range, particularly at temperatures above 800 °C. This makes the GB model the preferred choice for predicting reduction factors in high-temperature scenarios, which are critical for industrial applications involving fire-exposed processes. This study aligns with recent advancements in ML-based material property predictions under extreme conditions. For example, Shafighfard et al. [10] used a stacked ML model to predict the compressive strength of SFRC under high temperatures, demonstrating ML's ability to process diverse datasets with high accuracy. While their focus was SFRC, our research extends these methods to high-strength steels (HSS) and their ultimate stress at elevated temperatures. Unlike their stacked approach, we found Gradient Boosting to be the most effective, achieving an adjusted R² of 0.98. Both studies highlight the importance of comprehensive data sources in enhancing ML model performance.

4. Concluding remarks

In this study, we conducted tensile tests on S235 steel with varying thicknesses and temperatures to develop an initial training dataset for a machine learning (ML) model aimed at predicting the reduction factor as a function of temperature and material thickness. The training dataset was subsequently expanded by incorporating over 450 reduction factor curves from various material classes and thicknesses. Several ML models, including Lasso Regression (LASSO), Gradient Boosting (GB),

Fig. 8. Comparison of experimental and literature-based training data for the reduction factor as a function of temperature for HSA800 material with 6 mm thickness.

Random Forest (RF), Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Support Vector Regression (SVR), and Adaptive Boosting (ADA), were employed to predict the reduction factor. Based on the results, the following conclusions were drawn regarding the performance of each model:

Gradient Boosting (GB) demonstrated the best performance, achieving an adjusted coefficient of determination (R²) greater than 0.98. This model's superior predictive ability can be attributed to its exceptional capability to model complex data dependencies and accurately capture the nonlinear behavior of the reduction factor, particularly at both low and high temperatures. The results suggest that GB is a robust approach for modeling material behavior under varying conditions.

Random Forest (RF) also yielded strong predictive results, showing a high degree of accuracy in capturing nonlinear relationships. This model is particularly robust against overfitting and is well-suited for datasets with both linear and nonlinear features. However, it is less interpretable than other models such as LASSO.

Adaptive Boosting (ADA) performed comparably to GB, providing accurate predictions, especially for complex, nonlinear data. While it showed promise, it can be more sensitive to noise and outliers, which may affect its robustness in certain scenarios.

Lasso Regression (LASSO) a linear regression-based model, provided unsatisfactory results in this study. Its performance was significantly lower than that of the other models, highlighting the limitations of linear models when applied to complex, nonlinear systems such as the reduction factor prediction.

Support Vector Regression (SVR) another regression-based model, also underperformed in comparison to the tree-based models. While SVR is effective in certain contexts, it did not yield satisfactory results for this particular problem, especially when handling the nonlinear nature of the reduction factor across varying conditions.

This study emphasizes the potential of Gradient Boosting as a powerful and reliable tool for predicting material properties, particularly in scenarios involving complex, nonlinear relationships. The findings also suggest that tree-based models, such as Random Forest and Adaptive Boosting, are well-suited for similar predictive tasks, while linear models like LASSO and SVR may not provide adequate accuracy for the prediction of the reduction factor under the conditions examined.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

C. Yazici: Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **F.J. Domínguez-Gutiérrez:** Writing – original draft, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: F. Javier Dominguez Gutierrez reports financial support was provided by National Centre for Nuclear Research. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary material related to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rineng.2025.104242>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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